

IDENTIFYING FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AMONG CREATIVITY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract: In this article, the factors influencing the scientific and research activities of teachers of the school of creativity are considered in a complex. The internal and external factors contributing to the development of scientific research, as well as factors hindering this process, are analyzed. Based on the research results, practical recommendations for the development of scientific research are being developed.

Keywords: school of creativity, scientific research, motivation, pedagogical skills, scientific potential, innovation, education system, staff qualifications, scientific activity, research, management.

In our country, significant attention is being given to the education system to ensure that students acquire modern knowledge and vocational skills in line with global standards. Extensive efforts are being systematically implemented to help them grow into physically and mentally mature individuals, unlock their abilities and talents, and foster a sense of patriotism, humanity, and dedication to their profession.

In the modern education system, the role of teachers has changed considerably; they are no longer just knowledge providers but also active researchers and promoters of innovative ideas. This trend is particularly evident in creativity schools, where the quality of education is directly linked to the scientific potential of teachers.

Teachers in creativity schools can enhance the educational process by generating new knowledge in their respective fields, developing advanced pedagogical technologies, and applying them in practice. Across different regions of the world, the concept of creativity has played a fundamental role in the advancement of human culture, as well as in the development of natural sciences, philosophy, arts, and humanities.

Creative thinking differs from random thinking; it is a genuine competence based on knowledge and experience, enabling individuals to achieve expected outcomes even in complex and challenging situations.

Extensive reforms in Uzbekistan's education sector are aimed at enhancing teachers' professional skills and engaging them in scientific research. However, in practice, the research activities of creativity school teachers are still underdeveloped. Identifying the causes of this issue and determining the factors that hinder the development of teachers' scientific potential is of great importance.

An analysis of scientific literature on this issue reveals that many researchers have focused on the factors influencing teachers' scientific activities. For instance, G. Toychiyeva studied the development of teachers' professional competence, while N. Muslimov explored the integration of pedagogical innovations into the educational process. Among international

scholars, J. Hattie made significant contributions to understanding the relationship between teacher influence and educational outcomes.

However, the specific characteristics of developing scientific research activities among teachers in creativity schools remain insufficiently studied. Therefore, the goal of this research is to identify the factors that influence the development of scientific research among creativity school teachers.

Factors Influencing Scientific Research in Education

Scientific research is a purposeful activity aimed at generating new knowledge, expanding existing knowledge, and solving practical problems. It includes the following stages: identifying the problem, analyzing literature, formulating a hypothesis, collecting empirical data, analyzing the data, and drawing conclusions.

Analysis of the Scientific Activities of Creativity School Teacher

Creativity schools are unique educational institutions that place special emphasis on developing students' creative abilities. Teachers in these schools must not only possess high pedagogical skills but also actively engage in scientific research.

In practice, the scientific activities of creativity school teachers manifest in various ways. Some teachers write research articles, participate in conferences, and implement scientific projects, while others focus primarily on developing educational and methodological materials.

Surveys and observations indicate that most teachers in creativity schools show an interest in scientific research. However, many of them lack sufficient time and resources to actively engage in it. Additionally, the shortage of scientific supervisors, weak methodological support, and an inadequate incentive system hinder teachers from fully realizing their scientific potential.

Factors Influencing the Development of Scientific Research

The factors affecting the development of scientific research among creativity school teachers can be categorized into the following groups:

Internal factors: Personal motivation and interest, research capability, pedagogical skills, and a commitment to self-improvement.

External factors: Support from school administration, availability of financial resources, guidance from scientific supervisors, methodological support, incentive systems, and connections with the scientific community.

Each of these factors directly influences a teacher’s engagement in scientific research. While a teacher’s interest and motivation drive research efforts, support from school administration and the availability of financial resources create the necessary conditions for conducting research

Factors Influencing Scientific Research Skills in Teachers

Practical Recommendations for Enhancing Scientific Research Among Creativity School Teachers

Based on the research findings, the following practical recommendations can be proposed to foster scientific research among creativity school teachers:

Establish scientific councils in schools and organize their activities effectively.

Encourage teachers to participate in scientific conferences and support the publication of their research articles.

Organize scientific seminars and training sessions to equip teachers with research methodologies and techniques.

Assign scientific supervisors to teachers and provide them with methodological support.

Provide additional financial compensation for teachers engaged in scientific research and establish a system of material and moral incentives.

Supply school libraries with scientific literature and grant teachers access to academic databases.

Foster collaboration with higher education institutions and research centers, encouraging teachers to participate in scientific projects.

In conclusion, the development of scientific research among creativity school teachers is a complex and multifaceted process that requires not only personal interest and dedication but also strong support from school administration and the government. The practical recommendations presented in this article aim to create a scientific environment in creativity schools, enhance teachers' research potential, and improve the overall quality of education.

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